

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GAME-BASED LEARNING FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO IPER (THE INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH) PHARMACY STUDENTS

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Abstract The aims of this article were to test and to evaluate a game-based learning (GBL) approach for teaching English to IPER pharmacy students. GBL model was applied in a fifteen-week semester English course for first-year institute pharmacy students. The course met once a week for two hours. During each class, the students were divided into small groups of 4–5 to participate in three educational games related to vocabulary, pronunciation, and sentence creation. At the completion of each game, the teacher held a discussion with the students. The effectiveness of the game-based model was evaluated by a pre-test at the start of the semester and a post-test at the end of the semester. Both tests covered knowledge of vocabulary, knowledge of grammar, and self-assessment of vocabulary and grammar competency. Pronunciation skills were evaluated in the semester midterm and final exams.

Key words: GBL, research, grammar, knowledge, skills, competency, vocabulary, IPER

Introduction

English plays an important role in pharmacy studies and careers. Inadequate English communicative skills could result in several drawbacks in education and work situations since most textbooks and professional journals are written in

English. A lack of vocabulary knowledge could impede text processing and result in relatively low English reading ability. Students might ignore the words they do not know or misunderstand the context. Additionally, English is used to communicate with foreign patients and health care professionals. Therefore, hospital and community pharmacists need to be able to listen and speak English proficiently. Moreover, correct pronunciation is one of the factors that promote comprehensible communication. Mispronounced words might lead to misunderstanding and adverse outcomes.

Pharmacy students in Uzbekistan are faced with several obstacles in learning English. Most students do not have sufficient vocabulary knowledge or mispronounce words. Some students cannot use vocabulary for sentence construction. These obstacles result in poor communicative English competency. English learning for pharmacy students at IPER consists of three courses. The first course is Communicative English for Specific Purpose. The overall goal of this course is to improve students' English listening and speaking skills with the emphasis on vocabulary, pronunciation, and sentence creation for academic and professional purposes. With sufficient vocabulary knowledge, students subsequently proceed to the second course, Communicative English for Academic Analysis, which focuses on summarizing, analyzing, interpreting, and expressing opinions using English. The last course, Communicative English for Research Presentation, allows students to practice giving an oral presentation on academic research related to pharmacy areas.

Based on the outlined curriculum, developing and expanding vocabulary is a fundamental step to becoming a proficient English user. Gaining vocabulary knowledge is an incremental process. Students must practice using words several times to get such words into memory. Conventional vocabulary learning by reciting and writing words is tiresome. Students' negative impressions on the first course might lead to the failure of subsequent courses. Evidence shows that game-based

learning (GBL) has several benefits to learners. This has led to the implementation of GBL into vocabulary teaching of the first English course taught to pharmacy students at IPER. The objective of this article was to determine the outcomes of applying a GBL approach to teaching English to IPER pharmacy students. However, this study did not specifically aim to determine whether GBL is better than the conventional English teaching method.

Literature Review

Game-Based Learning

GBL is a process designed to cover subjects of interest by incorporating gameplay (Plass, Perlin, & Nordlinger, 2010). This model creates an environment that enhances knowledge and skills acquisition (McFarlane, Sparrowhawk, & Heald, 2002). Play is important in cognitive development and learning. It can motivate students to stay focused on the study (Plass, Homer, & Kinzer, 2015). Evidence has shown a close relationship between learning motivation and outcomes (Huang, Huang, & Tschopp, 2010). A series of game features that have a motivational nature includes incentive structures (e.g. stars, points, badges, or trophies), game mechanics, and activities enhancing learners' enjoyment (Hidi & Renninger, 2006; Huang et al., 2010; Plass et al., 2015). Moreover, GBL can influence learners' attitudes towards learning (Qian & Clark, 2016) and decrease students' anxiety in class (Yolageldili & Arikan, 2011). A study has shown that a GBL approach has a significant impact on learning achievements (Cheng & Su, 2012).

Game-Based Learning in an English Course

Learning vocabulary in isolation by reciting is tiresome. One of the approaches used to encourage learners' engagement and participation in the course is the implementation of GBL. Evidence has shown that learners' participation in the course can assist their ability to learn and retain new words (Derakhshan & Khatir, 2015; Huyen & Nga, 2003). Moreover, implementation of GBL in vocabulary

learning brings real-world context into the classroom by enhancing students' use of English in a communicative way (Derakhshan&Khatir, 2015).

Several examples of using GBL in an English course are summarized as follows. Aslanabadi and Rasouli found that the implementation of games improved Iranian vocabulary knowledge in kindergartens (Aslanabadi&Rasouli, 2013). Online language teaching games and regular teaching were implemented in the experimental and control group, respectively. The results showed several benefits of games e.g. increase learners' motivation and improvement of learners' confidence. Further, the effects of instructional games on facilitating students' vocabulary learning were examined by Dolati and Mikaili (Dolati&Mikaili, 2011). Pre-test and post-test were used to evaluate the effects of games. Positive outcomes were reported. They also identified that games can motivate and engage learners in the learning process, particularly students who are quiet and passive. The effectiveness of games was also confirmed by a study Efendi conducted in a group of seventh grade students (Efendi, 2013). In this study, he found that the use of "Got It Game" and "Back to the Board Game" can improve learners' vocabulary mastery achievement. Moreover, Turgut and Irgin reported that online computer games can promote learning engagement and vocabulary skills (Turgut &İrgin, 2009). Though several benefits of GBL implementation in an English course have been reported, most studies that determined the effectiveness of GBL were conducted in primary or secondary school because it is well received that games fit the nature of children. The effectiveness of the implementation of GBL in an English course at higher levels, particularly in pharmacy students is limited. Therefore, we aimed to determine the outcomes of applying GBL in teaching English to IPER pharmacy students.

Methodology

Study Design and Participants

This study evaluated the outcomes of a GBL approach employed in the Communicative English for Specific Purpose course taught to second-year pharmacy students at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Naresuan University, Thailand. All of them were taught with the same lesson plan and content during the course. This study followed the exemption criteria of IPER.

Class Activities and Game-Based Learning Approach Employed in This Course. The game was designed based on the course objectives, characteristics of the students as well as classroom resources and environment. The course objectives are to practice listening and speaking English with an emphasis on pronunciation, vocabulary, and sentence structures for academic and professional purposes. However, the main limitation of teaching English to the students is class size, with approximately 20 students per 1 instructor. The instructor cannot interact with each student thoroughly and equally. Moreover, learners do not have enough opportunities to interact in the English language. Therefore, a game that can engage all student participation to increase collaborative and interactive learning tasks was designed. Also, the designed game was inexpensive and suitable for the available classroom resources.

Lists of vocabulary essential for pharmacy education and careers consisting of 50 vocabulary words for each weekly class were collected and categorized according to their typical usage. These lists were provided to the students at the beginning of the course. Before each weekly class, all students reviewed and searched for the meaning of the assigned words. In addition, a list of essential grammar at a beginner to intermediate level was selected and provided to students at the beginning of the course for use in sentence construction. A total of fifteen grammar items were included in the course and were used throughout the semester. Students reviewed the assigned grammar for that week before attending the class. During the class each week, students were divided into small groups of 4–5 members. Each group completed three games, including pronunciation games,

vocabulary games, and sentence creation games, sequentially. For details on each game, students in each group were asked to sit in a circle facing each other. Students were asked to write down each word from the assigned vocabulary list of each week on a small card. All cards were pooled facing down in the middle of a circle. Each student chose one card and shared it with the group. The group then guessed the meaning of the chosen word. The students who got the correct meaning scored a point. Students were allowed to use a dictionary to check for correctness. This process was continued for 25 minutes. The same procedure was applied to the pronunciation game. For the pronunciation game, the correctness on pronunciation was checked with an online dictionary by other members of the group. At the end of the pronunciation game, the instructors randomly chose the words commonly mispronounced for discussion with the class. Regarding the sentence creation game, all members of a group worked together in constructing sentences. Students had to use the provided grammar list to create the sentences. All created sentences were submitted to the instructors after the end of the game. Certain sentences, particularly those that were complex, were selected for a class discussion.

Outcome Measurements and Statistical Analysis

The outcomes of a GBL approach were evaluated on four domains, including (1) pre- and post-self-assessment, (2) pre- and post-vocabulary tests, (3) pre- and post-grammar tests, and (4) two pronunciation exams (on week 8 and week 15). Self-assessment was evaluated using a questionnaire reviewed by 2 experts consisting of two domains: grammar (five items) and vocabulary (four items) knowledge. All items were evaluated using a five-point Likert scale to capture how the students felt about their vocabulary and grammar competency, ranging from 1 (very low competency) to 5 (very high competency). Vocabulary tests were evaluated using multiple-choice exam combining synonym and antonym questions. Assessment of grammar knowledge was performed using error recognition tests. Regarding pronunciation exams, each student was asked to pronounce 5 pre-selected words in

front of the instructor in the mid-term and the last week of the semester. A face to face discussion among the teachers on how the words are pronounced and how to give a score to a student was employed.

For statistical analysis, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test was used to determine the nature of the data. A paired Student's t-test or a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used for normally distributed and non-normally distributed data, respectively. Subgroup analyses categorized based on cumulative grade point average (GPA) was also performed. The cumulative GPA was classified into ≤ 3.0 , $3.0-3.5$, and > 3.5 . Data analysis was performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Statistical significance was assumed at a p-value of less than .05.

Results

Eighty-nine first-year pharmacy students enrolled in this course. Of these, eighty-seven students completed both pre- and post- vocabulary and grammar tests as well as two pronunciation exams. However, only fifty-five students completed pre- and post-self-assessment questionnaires. The results from the K-S test indicated that the scores of all pre-and post-assessments, as well as the two pronunciation tests, were not normally distributed. Therefore, a non- parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was employed for data analysis. Students got an average score of 7.43 out of 10 points on the pre-vocabulary test. The average score improved significantly to 8.82 ($p < .05$). Subgroup analyses showed that students with cumulative GPA $3.0-3.5$ and > 3.5 , but not with those whose cumulative GPA < 3.0 , had statistically significant improvement in vocabulary knowledge ($p < .05$). For grammatical knowledge, a slight improvement was observed, with the increase of the average score from 6.94 to 7.09 out of 10 points. However, such improvement was not statistically significant ($p = .302$). Similarly, the difference between pronunciation scores of the first and the second tests was not statistically significant ($p = .554$). A thorough observation of individual students showed that the score improvement on vocabulary and

grammar knowledge ranged from one to seven points and one to four points, respectively. Regarding pronunciation skills, the improved scores were in a range of one to three points.

As for the self-assessment, grammar competency scores exhibited a normal distribution. Thus, a parametric pair Student's t-test was used to analyze this part, whereas, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was utilized for the vocabulary competency. The average competency scores significantly increased from 14.56 to 17.58 and 11.35 to 14.35 for grammar competency and vocabulary competency, respectively. The majority of students rated themselves as having low competency on both grammar and vocabulary

Grammar

Self-assessment on grammar competency Self-assessment on vocabulary competency

Pronunciation (1st and 2nd exams)

knowledge during pre-assessment. Unsurprisingly, competency levels of both grammar and vocabulary knowledge shifted to moderate tier during post-assessment. The results of learning outcomes and students' self- assessment are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

The GBL approach has been implemented in various areas of education. Positive outcomes of such an approach have been documented including learning achievements, critical thinking skills, communication skills, positive attitudes, and motivations towards the course (Cheng & Su, 2012; Qian & Clark, 2016; Yien, Hung, Hwang, & Lin, 2011). This study aimed to determine the impact of the GBL approach implemented in a Communicative English for Specific Purpose course, focusing on students' learning outcomes.

The data showed that the implementation of a GBL approach resulted in a significant improvement in vocabulary knowledge, but not in grammar and

pronunciation competency, which could be because our GBL was mainly designed to improve vocabulary knowledge but not grammar or pronunciation knowledge.

However, there was a trend towards higher grammar score of post-assessment. The insignificant improvement in grammar proficiency could be due to different background knowledge in this area. In addition, students were assigned to review each grammar topic by themselves, which was not mandatory in this course. The different periods spent on the review might impact students' grammar proficiency. Moreover, providing that students were allowed to help each other in constructing sentences, those with a high level of grammar proficiency might dominate other members in the group and oppose individuals' attempts in learning sentence creation. Results of subgroup analyses indicated that students with a cumulative GPA of > 3.0 showed significant improvement in vocabulary knowledge following GBL implementation. The non-significant results observed in the group with cumulative GPA ≤ 3.0 could be due to insufficient power, with only 7 students in this group. However, there was a trend towards higher post-test scores. With sufficient power, the results of all subgroups should be consistent, which strengthens the positive impact of GBL on vocabulary knowledge.

Improvement in pronunciation scores could not be observed in this study. Given that the words selected for two pronunciation tests were different, this result was not unexpected. In addition, only 5 out of 375 vocabulary items were picked out for each pronunciation test, which might not be a good representative of the whole vocabulary. Pronunciation competence is a skill that needs long-term practice. The practicing period of only one course might not be able to improve such skill. In addition, the lack of routine English practice in daily life may be the main obstacle to the improvement of English communicative skills for our students. To be able to observe a substantial improvement in such skills, students should practice English not only in the class but also outside the classroom. However, the supporting environment for English usage in the faculty is quite limited since the students had

a full schedule in mandatory courses of pharmacy programs. Thus, they did not have much free time for practicing English. Moreover, most of these courses were taught in Uzbek/Russian. Therefore, students' chance of practicing English was restricted. Self-assessed competency on grammar and vocabulary indicated that IPER pharmacy students felt they had relatively low proficiency in both domains. Following the implementation of a GBL approach, learners' attitudes towards both domains improved significantly. These results strengthen the positive impact of applying a GBL approach to teaching English.

Implementation of GBL to English teaching to pharmacy classes in Uzbekistan is impeded by relatively large class sizes. Therefore, designing a game that enables all student participation is the main challenge. Several factors should be considered before initiating gameplay such as game complexity, class size, length of time, content, and targeted audience (Patel, 2008). Though, several studies reported students' positive satisfaction on the GBL approach (Patel, 2008; Rose, 2011; Sando, Elliott, Stanton, & Doty, 2013), some negative attitudes towards gameplay were also reported. Students who reported negative satisfaction felt overwhelmed with the games because they needed to learn how to play the games in addition to class materials (Patel, 2008). The game designed for the English class had several positive aspects. First, it was simple and explicit. All students could follow and participate in the game without extra burden. In addition, dividing students into small groups of 4-5 members could promote all students' participation in the game. This could promote the co-creation of knowledge among learners (Ghazal & Smriti, 2016). Second, the game length of approximately 20–25 minutes was suitable to sustain students' attention as well as enthusiasm. A too-long game might result in being bored and losing concentration. Third, the number of vocabulary items assigned to students each week was proper for students' free time. Students had sufficient time to review the assigned vocabulary before coming to the class. In addition, the continuous feedback provided by the teachers after each game

session provided progress on how well learners performed on each task. Last but not least, the designed class activities with three short games (pronunciation, vocabulary, and sentence creation games) rather than a single lengthy game, might be better in retaining students' concentration.

Some limitations of this study should be noted. First, this study was conducted without a control group of traditional English teaching. Further study on the effectiveness of a GBL approach consisting of a control group of traditional face to face English teaching should be conducted to clearly evaluate the impact of GBL over the traditional approach. Second, all of the games implemented in this study were quite similar, which might be tiresome for the students towards the end of the semester. A variety of games should be applied in this course to stimulate students' eagerness in class activities. Third, the designed game which was suitable for vocabulary learning was not suitable for grammar or pronunciation learning. Other game design should be implemented to improve such knowledge. Last but not least, the behavioral and motivational impact of GBL was not evaluated in this study. Even though it was partly reported in the course evaluation, not all students were required to provide feedback on these two domains. Therefore, a concrete evaluation of these domains could not be performed. Despite this, based on instructor observations throughout the course, students were satisfactorily motivated towards a GBL approach. Further research on the effects of a game- based language learning on behavioral and motivational impact should be warranted. Regardless of these limitations, this study offers positive evidence of a GBL approach to learning achievements.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This article reported the outcomes of applying a GBL approach to teaching English to IPER pharmacy students. The GBL approach improved vocabulary knowledge and may potentially enhance grammar proficiency. The results of this study could be used as a guide in designing games for English teaching. Future

research on the outcomes of GBL should be conducted using both experimental and control groups. In addition, its effects on behavioral and motivational outcomes should be evaluated.

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